

ISic1435

I.Sicily inscription 1435

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (cycladic, Naxos)

Object

statue

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 49401

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329724

1. Σομοροτίδα □ τῶ ἱατροῦ □ τῶ Μανδροκλέος □

2.

Edition: PHI333756

1. Σομοροτίδα □ τῶ ἱατροῦ □ τῶ Μανδροκλέος □ [τόδε σᾶμα].

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644978

EDCS 64800228

PHI 329724

Bibliography

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